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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a short overview of the production of the Q-SORT teaser video, which was conceived mainly for the Internet.

The video can be watched at:

<https://vimeo.com/327608696>

This deliverable will be updated periodically at a later phase of the Project, according to the Project's needs.

STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document comprises four chapters.

Chapter 1 is a short introduction, providing a brief overview of the philosophy with which the video and the overall strategy for mass communication were conceived.

Chapter 2 details the key steps in the production of the video.

Chapter 3 provides the link to watch the video.

Chapter 4 sums up the conclusions and the outlook for the project video.

1 INTRODUCTION: AIMS, TARGET AUDIENCE, DESIGN & COMMUNICATION PHILOSOPHY

Since the time when we were writing the Q-SORT Project proposal, the video teaser was conceived as a means to prime the interest of non-specialist Web users.

The last 14 years have marked a gradual but seemingly unstoppable shift in user preference towards sharing video over other types of content, which makes video the ideal means of dissemination for viral diffusion over the Web.

More specifically, we had envisioned that the main vehicle through which Q-SORT could reach mass audiences, and thus attract them to the Q-SORT webpage, would be the social networks.

The decision was made from the very start to make Q-SORT scientists and partner institutions the focus of the Q-SORT teaser video.

This also meant that the main target audience segment for the video would be comprised of science lovers and students.

Given today's overcrowded Internet scene, which is characterised by very short attention spans on the user's part, we aimed to make something impactful, so as to attract people's attention. To this end, the director sought several ways to build drama in the story being told.

However, at the same time, we also sought to convey the spirit of the project, i.e. a sense of challenge, of discovery, the idea of a high-risk yet exhilarating enterprise.

2 DEVISING AND PRODUCING THE Q-SORT PROJECT VIDEO

Various ideas for a short video for the general public were explored.

In particular, a visually lush cartoon version was extensively researched and storyboarded, but ultimately shelved in favour of something more accessible and easier to produce, based chiefly on newly-shot video.

A long time was devoted to honing the best possible script, able to convey with short and simple sentences not only the spirit of the project, but also, crucially, a sense of some of the scientific ideas behind it. The aim of all this of course was not so much to make public understanding of science through video (something for which longer production times -and therefore larger resources- would be needed) but rather to prime the viewer's curiosity by providing the gist of some of Q-SORT ideas. A subset of viewers is expected to click through the link at the end of the video and explore ideas further on the Q-SORT website.

The voice-over was also checked and approved by the main investigators in the Project.

Visuals were also extensively researched. In particular, various strategies had to be devised in order to convert the physical-modelling simulation outputs of the PI's various custom-made software pieces. The latter are a unique feature of Q-SORT and can provide scientifically-accurate visualisations of the electron beam as it goes through the various elements in the microscope column: lenses, holograms, electrostatic or magnetostatic sorters. Visuals thus included also a few short CGI animations.

The shoot was focused mainly on the Project's principal investigators. It also included coverage of the various Partners' labs. Sets were lit when necessary, in generally by augmenting existing light rather than changing it completely. A DoP and Steadicam operator were employed. Footage originated in 4K RAW for a 2K final master, a strategy which offers many advantages including respecting the Nyquist criterion for resolution. The edit was perfected on an Avid system and the final colour correction was done in DaVinci Resolve.

3 LINK TO THE Q-SORT PROJECT VIDEO

The Q-SORT Project video can be watched at the following link:

<https://vimeo.com/327608696>

4 CONCLUSIONS AND REMARKS

The teaser video will be used for social media communication. It will be updated and perfected as new worthwhile events and measurements will take place and be shot.

The planned second release of the video is being devised.

ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL